

Enhancing global sensitivity and uncertainty quantification in medical image reconstruction with Monte Carlo arbitrary-masked mamba

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ARTICLE INFO

MSC:

41A05

41A10

65D05

65D17

Keywords:

Medical image reconstruction

Mamba

Uncertainty

Wavelet

Deep Learning

ABSTRACT

Deep learning has been extensively applied in medical image reconstruction, where Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Vision Transformers (ViTs) represent the predominant paradigms, each possessing distinct advantages and inherent limitations: CNNs exhibit linear complexity with local sensitivity, whereas ViTs demonstrate quadratic complexity with global sensitivity. The emerging Mamba has shown superiority in learning visual representation, which combines the advantages of linear scalability and global sensitivity. In this study, we introduce MambaMIR, an Arbitrary-Masked Mamba-based model with wavelet decomposition for joint medical image reconstruction and uncertainty estimation. A novel Arbitrary Scan Masking (ASM) mechanism “masks out” redundant information to introduce randomness for further uncertainty estimation. Compared to the commonly used Monte Carlo (MC) dropout, our proposed MC-ASM provides an uncertainty map without the need for hyperparameter tuning and mitigates the performance drop typically observed when applying dropout to low-level tasks. For further texture preservation and better perceptual quality, we employ the wavelet transformation into MambaMIR and explore its variant based on the Generative Adversarial Network, namely MambaMIR-GAN. Comprehensive experiments have been conducted for multiple representative medical image reconstruction tasks, demonstrating that the proposed MambaMIR and MambaMIR-GAN outperform other baseline and state-of-the-art methods in different reconstruction tasks, where MambaMIR achieves the best reconstruction fidelity and MambaMIR-GAN has the best perceptual quality. In addition, our MC-ASM provides uncertainty maps as an additional tool for clinicians, while mitigating the typical performance drop caused by the commonly used dropout.

1. Introduction

Medical imaging reconstruction stands as one of the most fundamental and pivotal components of medical imaging. High-quality and high-fidelity reconstructed medical images ensure the precision and effectiveness of subsequent disease diagnosis and treatment planning, thus reducing potential risks to patient health (Wang et al., 2020).

Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) provides high-resolution and reproducible assessments without exposure to radiation. Fast MRI is widely utilised to produce MR images from sub-Nyquist sampled k -space measurements, aiming to speed up the inherently slow data acquisition process and eliminate artefacts (Liang et al., 2020; Hammernik et al., 2023; Huang et al., 2024b). X-ray Computed Tomography

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Fig. 1. (A) Comparison between Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), Vision Transformers (ViTs), and VMamba. CNNs and ViTs represent two predominant paradigms, each possessing distinct advantages and inherent limitations: CNNs exhibit linear complexity with local sensitivity, whereas ViTs demonstrate quadratic complexity with global sensitivity. The emerging VMamba (Liu et al., 2024) has shown superiority in computer vision tasks, combining the advantages of linear scalability and global sensitivity. (B) Comparison between dropout and the proposed Arbitrary Scan Masking (ASM) mechanism. Dropout requires careful hyperparameter tuning (dropout rate) and typically leads to a performance drop in low-level tasks, despite its ability to mitigate overfitting in high-level tasks. The proposed ASM mechanism presents a superior alternative to dropout. Instead of randomly “dropping” some activations that may be essential for the final outcome, our ASM strategically “masks out” a part of redundant information during training and inference stages.

(CT), while capable of producing high-quality and detailed images, involves radiation risks. Sparse-view CT (SVCT) has been developed to reduce radiation doses by using fewer projection views, albeit at the risk of introducing significant artefacts (Shah and Platt, 2008; Pan et al., 2009). Positron Emission Tomography (PET), critical for understanding metabolic and functional body processes, often requires long scan times or high doses for quality imaging, leading to discomfort and risk. To address this challenge, the development of low-dose PET (LDPET) presents a promising avenue to enhance image quality without increasing the injected doses (Knopp, 2020).

A key research topic and challenge for medical image reconstruction is developing an effective, efficient, and reliable reconstruction model. Rapid advancement of artificial intelligence has propelled the development and widespread application of deep learning-based medical image reconstruction. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Vision Transformers (ViTs) (Dosovitskiy et al., 2020) represent the predominant paradigms that have achieved remarkable success in various vision tasks and are widely used in the medical imaging field. However, both CNNs and ViTs possessed their distinct advantages and inherent limitations.

Convolutional Neural Networks excel at capturing visual features especially in identifying local patterns, taking advantage of their hierarchical architecture and inductive biases. The shared weight mechanism makes them more parameter-efficient than multilayer perceptrons (MLPs). However, despite their powerful feature extraction capabilities and linear complexity, as Fig. 1(A) illustrated, CNNs typically exhibit local sensitivity and a lack of long-range dependencies, limiting their ability to contextualise global features. Vision Transformers (Dosovitskiy et al., 2020), characterised by their large receptive fields and global sensitivity, often outperform CNNs in capturing extensive contextual information. Nonetheless, as Fig. 1(A) shown, their significant computational demand, due to the quadratic complexity of the self-attention mechanism (Liu et al., 2024), limits their practicality for medical image reconstruction. Recent Transformer-based models for

medical image reconstruction have sought to mitigate these limitations by: (1) adopting a trade-off strategy that applies the self-attention mechanism within shifting windows rather than across the entire feature map (Liang et al., 2021; Huang et al., 2022a); (2) constructing hybrid models that incorporate CNNs (Chen et al., 2021) or Swin Transformers (Liu et al., 2021), applying ViT blocks only within deep, low-resolution latent spaces (Chen et al., 2021; Huang et al., 2022c).

As a powerful alternative, the emerging Mamba (Gu and Dao, 2023) originating from natural language processing (NLP), combines the advantages of both CNNs and ViTs. Mamba exhibits superior efficiency in managing long-sequence modelling due to its linear complexity and enhancement through hardware-aware optimisations. This efficiency positions Mamba as a viable contender to the prevalent self-attention mechanisms found in Transformers, particularly for tasks involving the processing of high-resolution visual data, as Fig. 1(A) illustrated.

In this study, we aim to explore the potential of Mamba in the field of medical image reconstruction, and propose MambaMIR, a Mamba-based model for joint medical image reconstruction and uncertainty estimation. According to Fig. 1(A), MambaMIR has global sensitivity with linear computational complexity, especially beneficial for low-level tasks such as medical image reconstruction, which often necessitates handling long sequences (large spatial resolutions) and maintaining global sensitivity.

In medical image reconstruction, uncertainty estimation is presented as an essential confidence assessment, providing additional information to the clinician by highlighting critical areas of concern. Monte Carlo (MC) dropout is a commonly used uncertainty estimation method, relying on the randomness of dropout during the training and inference stages (Gal and Ghahramani, 2016). However, as Fig. 1(B) illustrated, dropout requires careful hyperparameter tuning for the dropout rate, which is usually sensitive to the reconstruction performance. Furthermore, dropout typically leads to a performance drop in low-level tasks like image reconstruction, despite its ability to mitigate overfitting in high-level tasks (Kong et al., 2022).

Fig. 2. (A) The proposed Arbitrary-Masked S6 (AMS6) block. An AMS6 block includes a Scan Expanding module, an Arbitrary Scan Masking module, an S6 module, and a Scan Merging module. (B) Uncertainty estimation with the proposed Arbitrary Scan Masking mechanism during inference. (C) The framework of the proposed MambaMIR.

In this study, we propose a novel Arbitrary Scan Masking (ASM) mechanism, presenting a superior alternative to dropout. Instead of randomly “dropping” some activations that may be essential for the final outcome, our ASM strategically “masks out” a part of redundant information during training and inference stage, as Fig. 2(A) illustrated. According to Fig. 2(B), during the inference stage, a distribution of the reconstruction results is collected, and uncertainty maps can be produced by the variance of the resulting distribution. Our proposed MC-ASM method demonstrates its superiority over the commonly used MC dropout by generating an uncertainty map without requiring hyperparameter tuning. In addition, it avoids the performance degradation often seen when using dropout for low-level tasks.

Our proposed MambaMIR is a generalised framework for joint medical image reconstruction across different image modalities and uncertainty estimation (Fig. 2(C)). To the best of our knowledge, MambaMIR is the first Mamba-based model applied to medical image reconstruction. In addition, for the texture information preservation, a wavelet decomposition mechanism is employed in the proposed MambaMIR within both the image space and the latent space. For better perceptual quality, we further explore its variant based on the Generative Adversarial Network (GAN), namely MambaMIR-GAN.

Experiments have shown that the proposed MambaMIR and MambaMIR-GAN outperformed other baseline and state-of-the-art

(SOTA) methods for three medical image reconstruction tasks, including fast MRI, SVCT, and LDPET. In addition, the use of the Monte Carlo-based Arbitrary Scan Masking mechanism (MC-ASM) provided uncertainty maps as an additional tool for clinicians, while mitigating the typical performance drop caused by conventional dropout.

Our main contributions are summarised as follows:

- We propose an innovative Mamba-based model, namely MambaMIR, for joint medical image reconstruction and uncertainty estimation (Fig. 2(C)). To the best of our knowledge, MambaMIR is the first Mamba-based model applied to medical image reconstruction. MambaMIR inherits the advantage of global sensitivity and linear computational complexity from Mamba, especially beneficial for medical image reconstruction.
- We design a novel ASM mechanism which introduces randomness by “masking out” redundant information for uncertainty estimation. Compared to the commonly used MC dropout, our proposed MC-ASM provides an uncertainty map without the need for hyperparameter tuning and mitigates the performance drop typically observed when applying dropout to low-level tasks.
- We employ the wavelet transformation in our proposed MambaMIR and explore its GAN-based variant, for further texture preservation and better perceptual quality.

- Experiments have shown that MambaMIR achieved SOTA for three medical image reconstruction tasks, including fast MRI, SVCT, and LDPET. In addition, our proposed MC-ASM provided uncertainty maps as an additional tool for clinicians while mitigating the typical performance drop caused by the conventional dropout.

This manuscript is structured as follows: Section 1 introduces our work and highlights the importance of medical image reconstruction. Section 2 reviews related works across deep learning in medical image reconstruction, wavelet transformations, uncertainty estimation, and the Mamba model. Section 3 describes our methodology, detailing the architecture of MambaMIR, wavelet decomposition mechanisms, and the MC-ASM. Section 4 elaborates on the experiments, including dataset details, implementation, comparison results, and ablation studies. Section 5 discusses our experimental findings, highlighting the superiority of our proposed model. Section 6 concludes the paper, summarising our contributions and outlining potential future research directions.

2. Related work

2.1. Deep learning-based medical image reconstruction

Deep Learning-based medical image reconstruction has witnessed significant advancements in recent years, with a diverse range of models and methodologies developed, which can be broadly categorised into three main paradigms: enhancement-based methods, unrolling-based methods and generative model-based methods (Hammernik et al., 2023).

Enhancement-based methods, such as CNNs and Transformers, represent a data-driven approach in medical imaging by mapping subsampled data to the fully-sampled equivalents in an end-to-end style. This methodology sidesteps the traditional requirement for explicit modelling of acquisition physics, enabling a more streamlined and efficient reconstruction process. The effectiveness of this strategy is underscored by its application across a diverse spectrum of imaging modalities, including MRI (Hyun et al., 2018; Huang et al., 2022a), SVCT (Xia et al., 2021; Yang et al., 2022b,a), and PET (Gong et al., 2018), where it has consistently demonstrated its ability to accurately reconstruct images by learning a non-linear mapping.

Unrolling-based methods represent another innovative approach by integrating trainable parameters and neural networks into unrolled iterative reconstruction algorithms, such as those based on the Alternating Direction Method of Multipliers (ADMM). In doing so, these models can enforce data consistency more effectively by incorporating elements of the physical model directly into the reconstruction process. The ADMM-Net, for example, exemplifies the potential of unrolling-based models by learning the transformation of images and nonlinear operators, demonstrating significant improvements in the reconstruction of subsampled MRI (Sun et al., 2016; Schlemper et al., 2017; Yang et al., 2018b), sparse-view CT (Xiang et al., 2021), and low-count PET images (Gong et al., 2019).

Unlike enhancement- or unrolling-based methods, generative models focus on generating fully-sampled images from a learnt distribution, potentially circumventing the need for paired data during training. This category includes variational autoencoders, GANs, and diffusion models, each contributing uniquely to the field. These models leverage the power of generative algorithms to simulate realistic high-quality medical images, offering a promising avenue for image reconstruction. The flexibility and generative capacity of these models have attracted attention, recent research illustrating their potential medical image reconstruction, by embracing the inherent variability and complexity of medical data (Zhao et al., 2023).

2.2. Wavelet transformation in image restoration

Discrete wavelet transform (DWT) decomposes the signal into a set of wavelets with characterisation of both frequency and location. This method is particularly impactful in the field of image reconstruction and enhancement, where it serves multiple functions. As a regulariser in advanced computational models, DWT guides optimisation towards convex objectives, which has been shown to be essential in unrolling networks and Plug-and-Play methods (Gu et al., 2022). Its ability to perform high-low-frequency decomposition enhances image processing tasks such as super-resolution by effectively suppressing noise and improving convergence through multi-scale representations (Yu et al., 2021). Moreover, integration of DWT into neural network architectures as part of downsampling and upsampling operations (Wu et al., 2023) enriches the network's ability to process images, reducing noise and artefacts for cleaner input. This incorporation is particularly advantageous for image inpainting and super-resolution (Yu et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2023). In optimisation and texture enhancement, wavelets contribute to the design of loss functions (Li et al., 2022; Yang et al., 2020), where low-frequency loss affects holistic quality, and high-frequency loss improves perceptual quality. This dual approach ensures that images not only exhibit high fidelity, but are also visually appealing and detailed.

2.3. Uncertainty estimation in medical image reconstruction

Uncertainty estimation is crucial in evaluating and understanding the predictions made by deep learning models, particularly in fields like medical imaging where precise and reliable predictions are vital (Zou et al., 2023). Bayesian Neural Networks (BNNs) (Kendall and Gal, 2017) present a framework for quantifying this uncertainty by placing a prior distribution over the model's weights. This approach allows BNNs to capture the inherent uncertainty in predictions, especially useful in ill-posed inverse problems where the objective is to reconstruct a fully-sampled image from limited measurements. However, the complexity of BNNs arises in their inference, as the marginal probability of the network weights cannot be directly computed.

Monte Carlo Dropout (Gal and Ghahramani, 2016) offers a practical solution to this challenge by approximating variational inference. By retaining dropout during both training and inference phases, MC Dropout enables the model to sample from its posterior distribution, thus estimating uncertainty by aggregating the outcomes of multiple forward passes. This method effectively integrates with variational autoencoders (Grover and Ermon, 2019) and diffusion models (Luo et al., 2023), enhancing their ability to quantify uncertainty.

Ensemble methods (Lambert et al., 2024) further extend the uncertainty estimation by leveraging the diversity across multiple models or configurations to infer the uncertainty. This technique captures a wider range of behaviours and biases within the models, offering a more comprehensive view of uncertainty. Although more resource-intensive, ensemble approaches enhance the robustness and reliability of uncertainty estimates, making them invaluable in applications requiring high confidence in model predictions.

2.4. State space model and Mamba

State Space Models (SSMs) have emerged as a foundational framework for the analysis of sequence data, inspired by systems theory which describes a system's dynamics through its state transitions (Gu et al., 2021). SSMs are typically characterised as linear, time-invariant systems that map an input sequence $x(t) \in \mathbb{R}^L$ to an output sequence $y(t) \in \mathbb{R}^L$ through a series of hidden states $h(t) \in \mathbb{R}^N$. These models can be expressed using linear ordinary differential equations:

$$\begin{aligned} h'(t) &= \mathbf{A}h(t) + \mathbf{B}x(t), \\ y(t) &= \mathbf{C}h(t) + \mathbf{D}x(t), \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$, $\mathbf{B} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times 1}$, and $\mathbf{C} \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times N}$ represent the learnable parameters, with $\mathbf{D} \in \mathbb{R}^1$ typically denoting a residual connection.

The structured state space sequence models (S4) (Gu et al., 2021) and more recent Mamba (Gu and Dao, 2023) are based on a discretised version of these continuous models:

$$\begin{aligned} h_k &= \bar{\mathbf{A}}h_{k-1} + \bar{\mathbf{B}}x_k \\ y_k &= \bar{\mathbf{C}}h_k + \bar{\mathbf{D}}x_k, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{A}}$, $\bar{\mathbf{B}}$, $\bar{\mathbf{C}}$, $\bar{\mathbf{D}}$ are the discretised parameter, transformed by a timescale parameter Δ :

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\mathbf{A}} &= e^{\Delta \mathbf{A}}, \quad \bar{\mathbf{C}} = \mathbf{C}, \quad \bar{\mathbf{D}} = \mathbf{D}, \\ \bar{\mathbf{B}} &= (e^{\Delta \mathbf{A}} - \mathbf{I})\mathbf{A}^{-1}\mathbf{B} \approx \Delta \mathbf{B}. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Mamba introduces a novel approach in the landscape of State Space Models (SSMs) with its Selective Structured State Space Sequence Models incorporating a Scan (S6) (Gu and Dao, 2023). This innovation allows for the dynamic parameterisation of the SSM, with parameters $\bar{\mathbf{B}}$, $\bar{\mathbf{C}}$, and Δ being derived directly from the input data x , enabling an input-specific adaptation of the model.

Mamba is considered a strong competitor to the Transformer due to its global sensitivity and linear computational complexity, and has been widely applied for various computer vision tasks. Zhu et al. (2024) introduced a Mamba-based and plain (ViT-style) vision backbone, i.e., Vim, innovatively adapting Mamba for non-causal visual sequence via bi-directional scans mechanism and position embedding strategy. Liu et al. (2024) proposed VMamba, a hierarchical (Swin Transformer-style) vision Mamba backbone. VMamba handles non-causal visual images by the novel cross-scan mechanism, converting images into four ordered patch sequences through integrating pixels from top-left, bottom-right, top-right, and bottom-left. Huang et al. (2024a) developed LocalMamba with a novel window-based local scanning mechanism, effectively capturing local information while maintaining a global sensitivity. In addition, differentiable architecture search (Liu et al., 2018) was utilised for learning an optimal combination of scan modes. Research on Mamba has also been extended to the higher-dimensional vision backbone (Li et al., 2024a,b), where more complicated and task-specific multi-dimensional scanning mechanisms were developed. Mamba-based models have been widely utilised for various downstream tasks across image segmentation (Ma et al., 2024; Ruan and Xiang, 2024; Wang et al., 2024), detection (Gong et al., 2024; Chen et al., 2024) and restoration (Guo et al., 2024; He et al., 2024; Zheng and Zhang, 2024).

3. Methodology

3.1. Medical image reconstruction

The forward acquisition process for medical images is described by:

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{n}, \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{C}^n$ represents the image of interest, $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{C}^m$ denotes the corresponding measurements, and $\mathbf{n} \in \mathbb{C}^m$ is the inevitable noise encountered during the measurement process.

Depending on the type of medical imaging, the forward operator \mathbf{A} can vary. For fast MRI, \mathbf{A} can be a subsampled discrete Fourier transform $\mathcal{F}_\Omega : \mathbb{C}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{C}^m$, sampling the k -space locations as specified by Ω . For SVCT, \mathbf{A} is represented by the Radon transform $\mathcal{R}_\Gamma : \mathbb{C}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{C}^m$, projecting targets into a sinogram under a selected set of imaging angles Γ . For LDPET, \mathbf{A} is represented by the detection probability matrix $\mathcal{R}_\Delta : \mathbb{C}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{C}^m$, detecting coincidence events of gamma photons in acquisition time Δ .

Generally, the goal of the reconstruction stage is to recover the ground truth \mathbf{x} from the undersampled measurements \mathbf{y} . This process can be formulated as an inverse problem:

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}} = \arg \min_{\mathbf{x}} \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}\|_2^2 + \lambda \mathcal{R}(\mathbf{x}), \quad (5)$$

where \mathcal{R} represents a class of regularisers, and λ is a balancing parameter. This formulation aims to minimise the discrepancy between the measured and predicted data while incorporating regularisation to impose prior knowledge or desired properties on the solution.

3.2. MambaMIR: Overall architecture

The proposed MambaMIR model adopts a U-shaped architecture, which incorporates modules for patch embedding and unembedding, along with M paired encoder and decoder residual blocks, each linked by corresponding skip connections. Within both the encoding and decoding pathways, each residual block consists of N Arbitrary-Masked State Space (AMSS) blocks and includes modules for wavelet-based downsampling and upsampling. In the bottleneck, two Wavelet-embedded AMSS (WAMSS) blocks and a single Attention block for deep feature extraction are employed. Furthermore, features derived from the wavelet decomposition of the initial input are integrated into the encoding pathway through the Wavelet Decomposition module.

3.3. Wavelet decomposition mechanism

To further improve reconstruction quality and texture preservation, wavelet decomposition mechanisms are incorporated into the proposed MambaMIR in various modules, inspired by Phung et al. (2023). The 2D DWT and the inverse DWT (iDWT) are two commonly used transformations in medical images. A 2D image X can be decomposed into four subbands carrying different frequency components via DWT, while iDWT can recover the 2D image X' from four subbands:

$$\begin{aligned} \{LL, HL, LH, HH\} &= \text{DWT}(X), \\ X' &= \text{iDWT}(\{LL, HL, LH, HH\}), \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where LL indicates the low-frequency subband, HL , LH and HH are three high-frequency subbands representing vertical, horizontal and diagonal features of the original image. For conciseness, we use H^+ to indicate these three high-frequency subbands.

3.3.1. Wavelet-based downsampling and upsampling module

Conventionally, pooling or stride convolution are two popular methods for feature maps spatial downsampling, while deconvolution and pixel shuffling are commonly utilised for spatial upsampling. In terms of DWT and iDWT, one essential characteristic is their inherent spatial downsampling and upsampling mechanism, where each subband has only half of height and width compared to the original image. Our proposed Wavelet-based Downsampling (WDown) and Upsampling (WUp) modules leverage DWT and iDWT, inherently enabling feature downsampling and upsampling, while disentangling different frequency components. In addition, the high-frequency skip connection is used between two paired WDown and WUp modules to transfer the high-frequency subbands ($H^+ : HL, LH, HH$). The WDown module can be mathematically written as:

$$\begin{aligned} X' &= \text{Conv}(\text{GN}(X_{\text{in}})), \\ \{X_{\text{skip}}, \dots\} &= \underbrace{\{LL, \dots\}}_{X_{\text{skip}}} = \text{DWT}(\text{Conv}(X_{\text{in}})) \\ \{X'', H^+\} &= \underbrace{\{LL', HL', LH', HH'\}}_{X''} = \text{DWT}(X'), \\ X''' &= \text{Conv}(\text{GN}(X'')), \\ X_{\text{out}} &= X''' + X_{\text{skip}}, \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where X_{in} and X_{out} are the input and output feature maps of the WDown module. H^+ is the high-frequency component that is transferred to the corresponding WUp module. Conv and GN indicate the

convolutional layer and group normalisation. The WUp module can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned}
X' &= \text{Conv}(\text{GN}(X_{\text{in}})), \\
X_{\text{skip}} &= \text{iDWT}(\{\text{Conv}(X_{\text{in}}), H^+\}) \\
X'' &= \text{iDWT}(\{X', H^+\}) \\
X''' &= \text{Conv}(\text{GN}(X'')) \\
X_{\text{out}} &= X''' + X_{\text{skip}},
\end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

where X_{in} and X_{out} are the input and output feature maps of the WUp module.

3.3.2. Wavelet decomposition and wavelet information fusion

To better preserve texture information, additional skip connections are used to integrate wavelet-derived information from the original image into the encoder's feature maps. In the wavelet information pathway, Wavelet Decomposition modules are utilised for wavelet information extraction and spatial downsampling to adapt the resolution of encoder feature maps, which can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned}
X' &= \{LL, HL, LH, HH\} = \text{DWT}(X_{\text{in}}), \\
X_{\text{out}} &= \text{Conv}(X'),
\end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

where X_{in} and X_{out} are the input and output of the Wavelet Decomposition module. The wavelet-derived information is further integrated into the encoding pathway, functioning similarly to skip connections, but specifically for wavelet features.

3.3.3. Wavelet AMSS

In addition, two additional WAMSS blocks are applied to enhance the feature extraction from low-frequency components by AMSS blocks, while attempting to preserve more high-frequency detail via skip connections, which can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned}
\{X', H^+\} &= \underbrace{\{LL\}}_{X'} \underbrace{\{HL, LH, HH\}}_{H^+} = \text{DWT}(X_{\text{in}}), \\
X'' &= \text{AMSS}(X'), \\
X_{\text{out}} &= \text{iDWT}(\{X'', H^+\}),
\end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

where X_{in} and X_{out} are the input and output of the WAMSS blocks.

3.4. AMSS block

The structure of the AMSS block follows the design of the Mamba block (Gu and Dao, 2023) and VSS block (Liu et al., 2024). The input of AMSS blocks goes through a layer normalisation step before being divided into two pathways. The first pathway follows a sequence of layers: a gating linear layer, a depth-wise convolution layer with a 3×3 kernel, a SiLU activation function (Ramachandran et al., 2017), an Arbitrary-Masked S6 (AMS6) block and another layer normalisation layer. Meanwhile, the second pathway involves a linear layer with a SiLU activation function. The results of these two pathways are combined by multiplication and then passed through a final gating linear layer to generate the output of the AMSS block. The AMSS Block can be mathematically written as:

$$\begin{aligned}
X' &= \text{LN}(X_{\text{in}}), \\
X'' &= \text{LN}(\text{AMS6}(\text{DWConv}(\text{Linear}(X')))), \\
X_{\text{gate}} &= \text{Linear}(X_{\text{in}}), \\
X_{\text{out}} &= \text{Linear}(X_{\text{gate}} \odot X'') + X_{\text{in}},
\end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

where X_{in} and X_{out} are the input and output of the AMSS blocks. DWConv is the depth-wise convolution layer, LN is the layer normalisation layer, and \odot is the Hadamard production.

3.5. Monte Carlo-based arbitrary scan masking

3.5.1. Arbitrary-masked S6 block

A challenge arises when using Mamba to process vision data. S6 inherently processes data in an ordered sequential style, where information integration is limited to data that has been sequentially processed. This characteristic aligns well with temporal NLP tasks, however, posing challenges for computer vision tasks where data is not strictly sequential. Existing methods have been developed to mitigate this challenge by re-ordering the visual sequence by various directions, meanwhile leading to redundancy in sequence information (Zhu et al., 2024; Liu et al., 2024).

In this study, we introduce the AMS6 block, a novel component aimed at improving the performance of State Space Models in processing visual data, as Fig. 2 illustrated. Our proposed AMS6 block incorporates the cross-scan mechanism (Liu et al., 2024), to adapt Mamba to medical image data, while leveraging the inherent redundancy for uncertainty estimation. The AMS6 block includes four key modules: the Scan Expanding module, the ASM module, the S6 module, and the Scan Merging module. The pseudo-code is presented in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 Arbitrary-Masked S6 Block

```

Input:  $X$  # feature map,  $X.\text{shape}: (B, C, H, W)$ ;
#  $B$ : batch size,  $C$ : channel,  $H$ : height,  $W$ : width;

# Scan Expanding Module
 $Xs \leftarrow \text{ScanExpand}(X)$  #  $xs.\text{shape}: (B, 4, C, H, W)$ 

# Arbitrary Scan Masking Mechanism
 $s \leftarrow \text{random\_int}(0, 4)$ 
 $Xs\_m \leftarrow Xs$  #  $Xs\_m.\text{shape}: (B, 4, C, H, W)$ ;
 $Xs\_m[:, s, :] \leftarrow \text{zeros\_like}(Xs[:, s, :])$ 

# S6 Module
 $Ys \leftarrow \text{S6}(Xs\_m)$  #  $Ys.\text{shape}: (B, 4, C, H, W)$ ;

# Scan Merging Module
 $Y \leftarrow \text{ScanMerge}(Ys)$  #  $Y.\text{shape}: (B, C, H, W)$ ;

Output:  $Y$  # feature map,  $Y.\text{shape}: (B, C, H, W)$ ;

```

The Scan Expanding module extends image patches across rows or columns, beginning from the upper-left or lower-right corner, transforming a single image into four distinct ordered sequences, as Fig. 2(A) illustrated. The expanding process results in a $4 \times$ expansion of an image, making it redundant because all scans contain identical information, with the only variation being the direction of the scan.

Randomness is introduced in the ASM module via arbitrary scan masking, which takes advantage of the redundancy of scans. This is achieved by nullifying the pixels in one out of the four scans randomly chosen, selectively masking-out information while keeping the original matrix shape unchanged. In this way, our ASM mitigates the performance drop typically observed when applying dropout to low-level tasks.

The S6 module is the core component of the AMS6 block, responsible for processing scan-expanded sequences. Subsequently, these processed scans are merged and re-organised into their original patch form by the Scan Merging module.

The integration within the AMS6 block enhances the image reconstruction process while introducing randomness for the further uncertainty estimation via MC-ASM mechanism.

3.5.2. Monte Carlo-based arbitrary scan masking mechanism

Our proposed MC-ASM achieves uncertainty estimation by producing a distribution of predictions (reconstruction) from a single input (subsampling images) during the inference stage, utilising randomness from ASM module, inspired by MC dropout (Gal and Ghahramani, 2016).

From a Bayesian perspective, the arbitrary masking procedure can be interpreted as a variational inference method to approximate the posterior distribution of a model's weights $p(\theta|D)$, which accounts for uncertainty after observing the data D , as expressed in the Bayesian theorem:

$$p(\theta|D) \propto p(D|\theta)p(\theta), \quad (12)$$

where $p(\theta)$ encodes our prior knowledge about the parameters before observing the data, and $p(D|\theta)$ represents the likelihood of the data given the parameters. The posterior predictive distribution is integral to Bayesian predictive modelling:

$$p(\mathbf{Y}|\mathbf{X}, D) = \int p(\mathbf{Y}|\mathbf{X}, \theta)p(\theta|D)d\theta, \quad (13)$$

where \mathbf{X} is the input and \mathbf{Y} is the resulting output.

In practice, MC-ASM approximates the posterior predictive distribution $p(\mathbf{Y}|\mathbf{X}, D)$ by repeatedly sampling from the model with ASM at the inference stage and obtaining a set of outputs $\{\mathbf{Y}_1, \mathbf{Y}_2, \dots, \mathbf{Y}_N\}$, corresponding to a diverse set of sub-models $\{\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_N\}$. The variance of these outputs can be used to quantify the model's predictive uncertainty:

$$\mathbb{E}[\mathbf{Y}|\mathbf{X}, D] \approx \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbf{Y}_i, \quad (14)$$

$$\text{Var}[\mathbf{Y}|\mathbf{X}, D] \approx \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (\mathbf{Y}_i - \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{Y}|\mathbf{X}, D])^2.$$

This formulation allows for an empirical estimate of the epistemic uncertainty associated with the predictions, providing additional information for clinicians.

3.5.3. Arbitrary scan masking is a special case of dropout

We next provide the theoretical guarantee for the proposed MC-ASM, demonstrating that the ASM mechanism can be regarded as a special case of dropout.

Proposition 1. *The Arbitrary Scan Masking mechanism can be regarded as a special case of dropout.*

Proof. Dropout is a common regularisation technique widely used in deep learning, which randomly and temporarily removes a fraction of neurons and their connections in certain layers according to a predetermined probability. In the actual implementation, dropout is typically applied to the output of a layer within a neural network:

$$X_{\text{Dropout}}^{(l)} = X^{(l)} \odot D^{(l)}, \quad (15)$$

where $X^{(l)}$ is the output of l th layer in the neural network with a shape of (B, C, H, W) and $X_{\text{Dropout}}^{(l)}$ is the result after dropout operation. $D^{(l)}$ is a mask for dropout with the same shape as $X_{\text{Dropout}}^{(l)}$. \odot is the Hadamard product. For simplicity, typically each component of the dropout mask $D_{b,c,h,w}^{(l)}$ independently follows a Bernoulli distribution:

$$D_{b,c,h,w}^{(l)} \sim \text{Bernoulli}(1 - p), \quad (16)$$

where p is a predetermined dropout rate.

For the proposed AMS6 block, the ASM mechanism can be written as:

$$X_{\text{AM}}^{(l)} = X^{(l)} \odot M^{(l)}, \quad (17)$$

where $X^{(l)}$ is the expanded feature map after Scan Expanding module at l th AMS6 block, with a shape of $(B, 4, C, H, W)$, and $X_{\text{AM}}^{(l)}$ is the result

after ASM mechanism. $M^{(l)}$ is a mask with the same shape of $X_{\text{AM}}^{(l)}$, which can be written as:

$$M_{b,s,c,h,w}^{(l)} = \begin{cases} 0, & s = s', \\ 1, & s \neq s', \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

$$s' \sim \text{Uniform}\{0, 1, 2, 3\},$$

where the index s' of masked scan is randomly selected in a uniform distribution from $\{0, 1, 2, 3\}$, and components belong to the corresponding scan are masked-out with zero value.

We demonstrate that the dropout and our ASM mechanism are inherently sharing the same mathematical form, and our ASM mechanism is a specially case of dropout with different ‘‘dropout selection’’ mechanisms. The minimum selection unit for typical dropout is a single matrix element, and the probability of each element is independent and follows a Bernoulli distribution controlled by a dropout rate of p . However, the minimum selection unit for the ASM mechanism is a scan, and the probability of each scan is not independent. \square

3.6. Optimisation scheme

Our proposed MambaMIR can be trained and tested in an end-to-end style, represented as $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_u = \text{MambaMIR}(\mathbf{x}_u)$, where \mathbf{x}_u and $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_u$ denote the subsampled input and the resulting reconstruction.

A hybrid loss $\mathcal{L}_{\text{Tot}}(\theta)$ is employed for model training, involving a Charbonnier loss (Lai et al., 2019) in both the image and frequency domains, which are presented as $\mathcal{L}_{\text{img}}(\theta)$ and $\mathcal{L}_{\text{freq}}(\theta)$, respectively. For better perceptual reconstruction quality, we pose an l_1 restriction on the latent space by a pre-trained VGG model $f_{\text{VGG}}(\cdot)$ (Simonyan and Zisserman, 2014) and have $\mathcal{L}_{\text{perc}}(\theta)$. These loss functions are defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\theta} \mathcal{L}_{\text{img}}(\theta) &= \sqrt{\|\mathbf{x} - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_u\|_2^2 + \epsilon^2}, \\ \min_{\theta} \mathcal{L}_{\text{freq}}(\theta) &= \sqrt{\|\mathcal{F}\mathbf{x} - \mathcal{F}\hat{\mathbf{x}}_u\|_2^2 + \epsilon^2}, \\ \min_{\theta} \mathcal{L}_{\text{perc}}(\theta) &= \|f_{\text{VGG}}(\mathbf{x}) - f_{\text{VGG}}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_u)\|_1, \\ \mathcal{L}_{\text{Tot}}(\theta) &= \alpha \mathcal{L}_{\text{img}}(\theta) + \beta \mathcal{L}_{\text{freq}}(\theta) + \gamma \mathcal{L}_{\text{perc}}(\theta), \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

where \mathbf{x} is the ground truth. ϵ in the Charbonnier loss is empirically set to 10^{-9} . The trainable network parameter of the proposed MambaMIR is denoted as θ . \mathcal{F} represents the Discrete Fourier Transformation. α , β and γ are parameters balancing different losses.

For the GAN-based variant, i.e., MambaMIR-GAN, our MambaMIR is applied as the generator G_{θ_G} parameterised by θ_G and a U-Net discriminator (Schonfeld et al., 2020) parameterised by θ_D for adversarial training. The adversarial loss $\mathcal{L}_{\text{adv}}(\theta_G, \theta_D)$ and the total loss for MambaMIR-GAN are written as:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\theta_G} \max_{\theta_D} \mathcal{L}_{\text{adv}}(\theta_G, \theta_D) &= \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{x} \sim p_{\text{r}}(\mathbf{x})} [\log D_{\theta_D}(\mathbf{x})] \\ &\quad - \mathbb{E}_{\hat{\mathbf{x}}_u \sim p_u(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_u)} [\log D_{\theta_D}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_u)], \\ \mathcal{L}_{\text{Tot-GAN}}(\theta_G, \theta_D) &= \mathcal{L}_{\text{Tot}}(\theta_G) + \eta \mathcal{L}_{\text{adv}}(\theta_G, \theta_D), \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

where η is the weighting parameter.

4. Experiments

4.1. Dataset

In this work, we used the FastMRI knee dataset (Zbontar et al., 2018) and Stanford knee MRI dataset (SKMTEA) (Desai et al., 2022) for fast MRI reconstruction, two distinct anatomical subsets from Low-Dose CT Image and Projection Datasets (Moen et al., 2021) for SVCT reconstruction, along with an in-house PET dataset for LDPET reconstruction.

4.1.1. MRI: FastMRI

For the FastMRI dataset (Zbontar et al., 2018),² we used 584 three-dimensional (3D) proton density weighted knee MRI scans with available ground truth, which were acquired with 15 coils without fat suppression. Within each case, 20 slices of 2D coronal-view complex-value images near the centre were utilised and centre-cropped to a resolution of 320×320 in the image space. We randomly divided all 2D slices into a training set (484 cases) and a testing set (100 cases). The officially emulated single-coil data were applied as complex-value ground truth.

4.1.2. MRI: SKMTEA

For the SKM-TEA dataset (Desai et al., 2022),³ 155 scans of 3D, quantitative double-echo steady-state knee MRI scans with available ground truth were applied in the experiments. To avoid including very noisy or void slices, 100 sagittal-view 2D single-channel complex-value echo #1 slices were chosen for each case. All slices were centre-cropped to 512×512 in the image space. We split 155 cases into a training set (86 cases), a validation set (33 cases) and a testing set (36 cases), following the official dataset splits.

4.1.3. CT: Low-Dose CT Image and Projection Datasets

For the Low-Dose CT Image and Projection Datasets (Moen et al., 2021),⁴ two subsets including (a) chest and (b) abdomen were applied. The chest subset consisted of low-dose non-contrast scans aimed at screening high-risk patients for pulmonary nodules, while the abdomen subset consisted of contrast-enhanced CT scans used to detect metastatic liver lesions. Each subset included 40 cases. We split scans in each subset into a training set (32 cases in chest scans; 32 cases in abdomen scans) and a testing set (8 cases in chest scans; 8 cases in abdomen scans). Sparse-view sinograms were generated in a fan-beam CT geometry, with 60 projection views and 736 detectors. The source-to-detector distance was set to 1000 mm, and the source-to-rotation-centre distance was 512 mm. The reconstructed image resolution was 512×512 pixels.

4.1.4. PET: Low-Dose PET

For Low-Dose PET reconstruction, we used an in-house PET dataset containing 103 subjects of whole-body imaging. The low-dose data were obtained by resampling the original data, simulating various acquisition times. The dose reduction factor (DRF) quantifies the data acquired within a reduced time window, reflecting the degree of radiation dose. The dataset was divided into a training set (82 cases) and a testing set (20 cases). The resolution of PET images is 192×192 pixels.

4.2. Implementation details and evaluation metrics

For the network hyperparameters, we applied 4 residual blocks symmetrically in the encoder and decoder paths, where each residual block consists of 2 AMSS blocks. The basic embedding channel is 180, with a multiplication factor of $\{1, 2, 2, 2\}$ from shallow to deep. We trained our proposed MambaMIR and MambaMIR-GAN on two NVIDIA A100 GPU (80 GB) and tested them on an NVIDIA RTX 3090 GPU (24 GB).

Both MambaMIR and MambaMIR-GAN were trained using Adam optimiser for 100,000 gradient steps with a batch size of 8. The balancing parameters α , β , γ and η were set to 15, 0.1, 0.0025 and 0.1. The initial learning rate was set to 0.0002, with a decay rate of 0.5 every 20,000 steps after 50,000th step. Specifically for MambaMIR-GAN, we used MambaMIR as generator and applied a U-Net-based discriminator (Schonfeld et al., 2020) for adversarial training.

² <https://fastmri.med.nyu.edu/>.

³ <https://aimi.stanford.edu/skm-tea-knee-mri/>.

⁴ <https://www.cancerimagingarchive.net/collection/ldct-and-projection-data/>.

Three metrics including Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR), Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM), and Learned Perceptual Image Patch Similarity (LPIPS) (Zhang et al., 2018a) were applied for reconstruction quality assessment.

4.3. Comparisons with the SOTA

In the experimental section, we compared our proposed MambaMIR and MambaMIR-GAN with baseline and SOTA methods for three different medical image reconstruction tasks, including fast MRI, SVCT and LDPET.

Experiments for fast MRI included an unrolling-based and CNN-based method, D5C5 (Schlemper et al., 2017), a CNN-based and wavelet-coupled method, MWCNN (Liu et al., 2019), Transformer-based methods, SwinMR (Huang et al., 2022a) and ReconFormer (Guo et al., 2024), GAN-based methods DAGAN (Yang et al., 2018a) and STGAN (Huang et al., 2022b), as well as a diffusion model-based method DiffuseRecon (Peng et al., 2022). Experiments were conducted on FastMRI at acceleration factors (AFs) of $\times 4$ and $\times 8$, and on SKMTEA at AFs of $\times 8$ and $\times 16$.

For SVCT, image domain methods DDNet (Zhang et al., 2018b) and FBPCConv (Jin et al., 2017), a sinogram domain method View-Interpolation (Inter) (Lee et al., 2017), a dual-domain method HD-Net (Hu et al., 2021), a parameter-learnable inverse Radon transform IRadonMap (He et al., 2020), a frequency-domain method FreeSeed (Ma et al., 2023) and an unfolding method RegFormer (Xia et al., 2023) were included. Results on abdomen and chest subsets were reconstructed from 60-view sinograms with uniform sampling.

For LDPET, we compared the proposed method with image enhancement-based methods U-Net (Ronneberger et al., 2015), an image denoising method REDCNN (Chen et al., 2017), a frequency domain-based method FFTFormer (Kong et al., 2023), and Transformer-based methods SwinIR (Liang et al., 2021) and SharpFormer (Yan et al., 2023). Quantitative results with DRF $\times 3$ and DRF $\times 6$ are presented.

All quantitative results for comparison studies can be found in Table 1. Visualised reconstruction samples can be found in Fig. 3 for FastMRI at AF $\times 4$, Fig. 4 for SKMTEA at AF $\times 8$, Fig. 5 for SVCT on chest scans, and Fig. 6 for LDPET at DRF $\times 6$. According to the results, our proposed MambaMIR and MambaMIR-GAN achieve comparable results or outperform current SOTA methods, where MambaMIR tends to provide results with better reconstruction fidelity, while MambaMIR-GAN presents results with superior perceptual experience.

4.4. Ablation studies

4.4.1. Component validity

To evaluate the validity of each component in the network architecture, ablation experiments, with the removal of a single component in each run, were performed on the FastMRI at AF $\times 8$ with a patch size of 2.

According to Table 2, we found that the utilisation of all components has a positive impact on the reconstruction results. Among them, the use of wavelet significantly improved model performance with only a slight effect on the model size. The use of MLPs in AMSS blocks and self-attention modules in the bottleneck, as two common designs in the network, was also shown to be effective.

To further evaluate the validity of wavelet decomposition, we conducted experiments comparing SwinMR (Huang et al., 2022a), STGAN (Huang et al., 2022b), and DiffuseRecon (Peng et al., 2022) with their wavelet-based counterparts. Specifically, for SwinMR and STGAN, we adapted the Residual Swin Transformer Block (RSTB) into a wavelet-based RSTB (WRSTB), similar to the modification of AMSS to WAMSS. For DiffuseRecon, we incorporated wavelet-based modules throughout the U-Net architecture.

Our experiments showed varied tendencies among methods when applying wavelet decomposition. For SwinMR and STGAN, the integration of wavelet components adversely affected the reconstruction quality. In contrast, for DiffuseRecon, the utilisation of wavelet components enhanced the reconstruction effectiveness.

Table 1

Quantitative results for comparisational studies for fast MRI, sparse-view CT (SVCT) and low-dose PET (LDPET) reconstruction. For fast MRI, experiments are performed on FastMRI at accelerate factor (AF) $\times 4$, $\times 8$, as well as SKMTEA at AF $\times 8$, $\times 16$. For SVCT, experiments are conducted on the abdomen and chest subsets from Low-Dose CT Image and Projection Datasets. For LDPET, experiments are conducted on in-house dataset with dose reduction factor (DRF) $\times 3$, $\times 6$. The best scores are indicated by **bold**.

Method	AF $\times 4$			AF $\times 8$		
	SSIM \uparrow	PSNR \uparrow	LPIPS \downarrow	SSIM \uparrow	PSNR \uparrow	LPIPS \downarrow
ZF	0.689 (0.083)*	28.79 (2.00)*	0.338 (0.050)*	0.580 (0.096)*	25.39 (1.79)*	0.504 (0.058)*
D5C5	0.740 (0.089)*	31.74 (2.70)*	0.168 (0.034)*	0.633 (0.105)*	28.80 (2.13)*	0.292 (0.039)*
DAGAN	0.722 (0.084)*	30.34 (2.11)*	0.216 (0.048)*	0.621 (0.097)*	27.98 (2.07)*	0.262 (0.043)*
MWCNN	0.766 (0.085)	32.36 (2.72)	0.179 (0.048)*	0.645 (0.109)*	29.84 (2.44)*	0.261 (0.052)*
SwinMR	0.747 (0.089)*	32.17 (2.83)*	0.161 (0.037)*	0.650 (0.105)*	29.82 (2.41)*	0.254 (0.043)*
STGAN	0.756 (0.086)*	31.81 (2.66)*	0.111 (0.034)*	0.679 (0.098)*	29.72 (2.32)*	0.155 (0.040)
DiffuseRecon	0.752 (0.088)*	32.22 (2.71)*	0.180 (0.030)*	0.660 (0.106)*	30.26 (2.39)*	0.287 (0.038)*
ReconFormer	0.754 (0.090)*	32.47 (2.96)*	0.155 (0.037)*	0.657 (0.106)*	30.12 (2.50)*	0.256 (0.037)*
MambaMIR	0.768 (0.087)	32.51 (2.83)	0.172 (0.051)*	0.680 (0.100)*	30.38 (2.47)	0.259 (0.061)*
MambaMIR-GAN	0.772 (0.087)	32.25 (2.77)*	0.109 (0.037)	0.704 (0.097)	30.24 (2.37)*	0.155 (0.044)

Method	AF $\times 8$			AF $\times 16$		
	SSIM \uparrow	PSNR \uparrow	LPIPS \downarrow	SSIM \uparrow	PSNR \uparrow	LPIPS \downarrow
ZF	0.597 (0.029)*	25.31 (0.84)*	0.462 (0.025)*	0.543 (0.032)*	23.33 (0.85)*	0.555 (0.027)*
D5C5	0.680 (0.028)*	28.36 (0.84)*	0.242 (0.030)*	0.615 (0.031)*	25.34 (0.80)*	0.371 (0.037)*
DAGAN	0.617 (0.032)*	26.60 (0.86)*	0.289 (0.038)*	0.544 (0.032)*	24.27 (0.84)*	0.375 (0.037)*
MWCNN	0.642 (0.033)*	28.89 (0.87)*	0.247 (0.026)*	0.559 (0.038)*	26.56 (0.94)*	0.329 (0.034)*
SwinMR	0.662 (0.031)*	29.23 (0.87)*	0.230 (0.025)*	0.566 (0.035)*	26.51 (0.89)*	0.318 (0.033)*
STGAN	0.706 (0.028)*	28.96 (0.86)*	0.138 (0.028)	0.629 (0.033)*	26.48 (0.89)*	0.209 (0.038)*
DiffuseRecon	0.646 (0.027)*	28.33 (0.81)*	0.202 (0.025)*	0.548 (0.029)*	24.96 (0.76)*	0.325 (0.034)*
ReconFormer	0.691 (0.028)*	29.81 (0.89)	0.212 (0.023)*	0.601 (0.032)*	27.01 (0.86)*	0.301 (0.033)*
MambaMIR	0.682 (0.029)*	29.49 (0.90)	0.237 (0.027)*	0.583 (0.035)*	27.12 (0.95)	0.312 (0.035)*
MambaMIR-GAN	0.712 (0.029)	29.06 (0.87)*	0.136 (0.026)	0.645 (0.033)	26.90 (0.93)*	0.198 (0.037)

Model	Abdomen			Chest		
	SSIM \uparrow	PSNR \uparrow	LPIPS \downarrow	SSIM \uparrow	PSNR \uparrow	LPIPS \downarrow
FBP	0.716 (0.041)*	31.88 (1.26)*	0.410 (0.035)*	0.550 (0.036)*	28.52 (1.02)*	0.440 (0.037)*
Inter	0.947 (0.008)*	40.96 (0.97)*	0.076 (0.018)*	0.847 (0.025)*	35.56 (1.02)*	0.155 (0.031)*
DDNet	0.941 (0.010)*	40.35 (1.00)*	0.090 (0.016)*	0.835 (0.027)*	35.41 (1.00)*	0.154 (0.023)*
FBPConv	0.929 (0.013)*	38.14 (1.09)*	0.175 (0.025)*	0.801 (0.035)*	34.13 (0.97)*	0.357 (0.050)*
IRadonMap	0.968 (0.007)*	43.32 (1.10)*	0.060 (0.015)*	0.868 (0.029)*	36.84 (1.16)*	0.135 (0.025)*
RegFormer	0.966 (0.007)*	42.64 (1.13)*	0.077 (0.021)*	0.850 (0.035)*	36.15 (1.14)*	0.226 (0.062)*
FreeSeed	0.967 (0.005)*	42.40 (0.98)*	0.061 (0.021)*	0.854 (0.044)*	35.97 (1.26)*	0.213 (0.048)*
MambaMIR	0.983 (0.005)	45.72 (1.31)	0.037 (0.016)*	0.874 (0.042)	37.18 (1.52)	0.160 (0.031)*
MambaMIR-GAN	0.977 (0.006)*	44.57 (1.29)*	0.024 (0.008)	0.854 (0.045)*	36.33 (1.56)*	0.049 (0.010)

Model	DRF $\times 3$			DRF $\times 6$		
	SSIM \uparrow	PSNR \uparrow	LPIPS \downarrow	SSIM \uparrow	PSNR \uparrow	LPIPS \downarrow
Subsampled	0.963 (0.034)*	38.62 (4.99)*	0.027 (0.024)*	0.923 (0.056)*	34.60 (5.00)*	0.068 (0.040)*
U-Net	0.951 (0.053)*	39.26 (4.75)*	0.027 (0.070)*	0.965 (0.029)*	38.00 (4.21)*	0.027 (0.030)*
REDCNN	0.976 (0.024)	40.37 (4.53)*	0.010 (0.013)	0.966 (0.030)*	38.50 (4.50)*	0.020 (0.023)
SwinIR	0.973 (0.026)*	39.72 (4.12)*	0.018 (0.016)*	0.953 (0.039)*	36.61 (3.88)*	0.044 (0.024)*
SharpFormer	0.959 (0.034)*	39.70 (4.49)*	0.018 (0.016)*	0.944 (0.038)*	36.61 (4.35)*	0.045 (0.023)*
FFTFormer	0.970 (0.025)*	41.07 (4.68)*	0.012 (0.018)*	0.958 (0.033)*	38.90 (4.50)*	0.021 (0.026)
MambaMIR	0.980 (0.020)	41.59 (4.71)	0.011 (0.017)	0.971 (0.026)	39.52 (4.58)	0.020 (0.026)
MambaMIR-GAN	0.978 (0.020)	41.16 (4.75)*	0.007 (0.015)	0.970 (0.025)	39.19 (4.57)*	0.010 (0.020)

* Denotes results that are significantly different from the best results by the Mann-Whitney Test ($p < 0.05$).

Fig. 3. Visualised results on FastMRI at AF $\times 4$. Ground truth (GT), undersampled zero-filled (ZF) images, reconstruction results and corresponding error maps are presented.

Fig. 4. Visualised results on SKMTEA at AF $\times 8$. Ground truth (GT), undersampled zero-filled (ZF) images, reconstruction results and corresponding error maps are presented.

Fig. 5. Visualised results for SVCT on the chest subset. Ground truth (GT), sparse-view images reconstructed by Filtered Backprojection (FBP), reconstruction results and corresponding error maps are presented. CT images are normalised within the range of $[-1024, 3096]$ HU for error map computation and display.

Fig. 6. Visualised results for LDPET at DRF $\times 6$. Ground truth (GT), low-dose images, reconstruction results and corresponding error maps are presented.

4.4.2. Hyperparameter

Ablation studies in the hyperparameter setting were conducted and presented in Fig. 7(A), exploring the patch size, the resolution of random cropping during training, and the number of S6's latent space channels.

Regarding the patch size, both the reconstruction performance (SSIM) and the computational cost (GFLOPs) increase as the patch size gets smaller. We can observe that the computational complexity of MambaMIR approximately increases linearly with the length of the sequence, consistent with theoretical predictions (patch size: $\times 2$, sequence length: $\times 4$, FLOPs: around $\times 4$). In our experiments, MambaMIR with a patch size of 1 is applied for benchmarking for a fair comparison,

while MambaMIR with a patch size of 2 was used for ablation studies due to hardware limitations.

In terms of the resolution of random cropping during training, the SSIM initially improves, reaching an optimal value before subsequently declining as the resolution increases, meanwhile, the FLOPs grow as the resolution increases. The optimal value exists since random cropping during training can be regarded as a data augmentation. We choose a resolution of 192×192 during training as a trade-off between performance and computational complexity.

For the number of latent space channels (#Channel) in S6, both the reconstruction performance (SSIM) and the computational cost (FLOPs)

Fig. 7. (A) Ablation studies on hyperparameters regarding the patch size, the randomly cropping resolution during training, and the number of S6’s latent space channels (#Channel); (B) Experiments comparing Mamba-based and Transformer-based models. The size of the data circle and the number below indicate the computational complexity (GFLOPs).

Table 2

Ablation studies for model component validity conducted on FastMRI at AF × 8. with a patch size of 2. Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM) and the number of parameter (#PARAMs) are reported to reflect the performance and model size. ‘FULL’: standard MambaMIR; WAMSS: Wavelet-embedded Arbitrary-Masked State Space Blocks; WDown/WUp: Wavelet-based downsampling/upsampling modules; MLP: Multilayer perceptrons in AMSS Blocks; Attn.: multi-head self-attention modules in the bottleneck; WRSTB: Wavelet Residual Swin Transformer Block.

Settings	SSIM	#PARAMs (M)
FULL	0.65403	50.227
WAMSS → AMSS	-0.00365	-0.000
WDown/WUp → Down/Up	-0.00407	-1.328
w/o Wavelet (Two Lines Above)	-0.00466	-1.328
w/o MLP	-0.00435	-9.175
w/o Attn.	-0.00353	-0.264
SwinMR	0.64952	11.402
SwinMR + WRSTB	+0.00005	+0.000
STGAN	0.67915	11.402
STGAN + WRSTB	-0.0065	+0.000
DiffuseRecon	0.69749	149.516
DiffuseRecon + Wavelet	+0.00315	+3.832

increase as #Channel increases. As a trade-off between performance and computational complexity, #Channel is set to 128.

4.5. Transformer v.s. Mamba

Mamba is regarded as a powerful competitor of Transformer. In this section, we further explored the comparison between our proposed MambaMIR and the Transformer-based counterparts.

To conduct a fair comparison, we replaced the AMS6 block in our proposed MambaMIR with multi-head self-attention (MSA) or shifted-window MSA (SWMSA), while preserving the rest components. We use “SxTy” to indicate the Transformer-based counterpart, where x is the number of SWMSA and y is the number of MSA in both the encoder and the decoder. Since MSA has much higher computational complexity than SWMSA, SWMSA is always applied in the shallower stages in our U-shape architecture. As reported in Fig. 7(B), the proposed MambaMIR outperforms all different Transformer-based counterparts and achieves a better Perception-Distortion Trade-off (Blau and Michaeli, 2018), while yielding a reasonable computational complexity.

5. Discussion

In this paper, we have proposed MambaMIR, an innovative Mamba-based model, along with its GAN-based variant, MambaMIR-GAN, for joint medical image reconstruction and uncertainty estimation. According to Table 1, MambaMIR-GAN tends to achieve the best LPIPS score and MambaMIR achieve the best PSNR score. It can be observed from the visualised examples (Figs. 5, 4, and 6) that MambaMIR-GAN tends

Fig. 8. Comparison of Effective Receptive Fields before and after training between the proposed MambaMIR and other methods for SVCT on abdomen subset.

Fig. 9. Quantitative comparison on FastMRI dataset between (1) MambaMIR without MC-ASM or MC dropout (control group), (2) MambaMIR with MC-ASM and (3) MambaMIR with MC Dropout using different dropout rates.

to produce more detailed texture information, while MambaMIR provides smoother reconstruction to ensure reconstruction fidelity, which satisfies a Perception-Distortion Trade-off (Blau and Michaeli, 2018). The experimental results have suggested that both MambaMIR and MambaMIR-GAN deliver superior performance in medical image reconstruction. In particular, MambaMIR tends to provide results with better reconstruction fidelity, while MambaMIR-GAN may provide reconstructions that better align with human perceptual qualities.

An essential advantage of our MambaMIR is its global sensitivity coupled with linear computational complexity. Fig. 8 presents the comparison of Effective Receptive Fields (ERF) (Luo et al., 2016) before and after training, between the proposed MambaMIR and other methods for SVCT on the abdomen subset. ERFs were introduced to describe the actual region of the model input in relation to its output, and are typically visualised through heatmaps, where the intensity of the colour indicates the strength of the influence of the input on the network’s output. According to Fig. 8, the ERFs of comparison methods such as Inter, DDNet, FBPCConv, and RegFormer are relatively concentrated

Fig. 10. (A) Visualised samples of uncertainty maps provided by MC dropout ($\alpha = 0.2$) and our MC-ASM, along with the corresponding error maps. (B) Quantitative comparison between (1) MambaMIR without MC-ASM or MC dropout (control group), (2) MambaMIR with MC-ASM and (3) MambaMIR with MC Dropout ($\alpha = 0.2$) on three datasets.

with a clear central peak, indicating a more localised receptive field. This concentration suggests that these methods predominantly focus on local features within the data. In contrast, the proposed MambaMIR displays a broader and more dispersed heatmap after training, indicating a larger receptive field, which demonstrates its superior global sensitivity and capacity to handle long-range dependencies.

In addition to the outstanding reconstruction results, our proposed MambaMIR can provide uncertainty maps through repeat sampling. These maps visually represent the model’s confidence in the reconstructed images, highlighting areas of potential uncertainty, which may signal regions with lower image quality or artefacts. As Fig. 10(A) illustrated, the high-uncertainty area for MRI knee reconstruction is located mainly in tissue with informative details (high-frequency area). For CT chest reconstruction, the high-uncertainty area indicated that the edges of tissue and bones have high uncertainty. For PET reconstruction, it can be observed that areas with higher radioactive concentrations demonstrate increased uncertainty. Figs. 9 and 10(B) present the quantitative comparisons evaluated on the FastMRI testset, including MambaMIR without MC-ASM (control group), MambaMIR with MC-ASM (proposed method) and MambaMIR employing MC Dropout at varying dropout rates. Experimental results have indicated that the utilisation of dropout leads to a consistent performance drop across various datasets at different dropout rates, the severity of which is positively correlated with the dropout rate. In contrast to MC dropout, our MC-ASM mitigates the performance drop while providing reasonable uncertainty maps without the need for hyperparameter tuning.

In response to observed discrepancies between the location of uncertainties and clinically relevant anomalies, we further investigated the performance of MambaMIR in pathological contexts. Specifically, we trained MambaMIR on a subset of the FastMRI dataset that included only healthy cases and subsequently tested it on a subset containing pathological cases, with annotations provided by the FastMRI+ dataset (Zhao et al., 2022).⁵ Fig. 11 presents uncertainty estimations for two subjects with bone lesions, meniscus tears, anterior cruciate ligament low-mod grade sprain and medial collateral ligament low-mod grade sprain. Experimental results have shown a notable alignment of

Fig. 11. Visualised samples of ground truth images with pathology annotation, annotated reconstruction error maps, and uncertainty maps provided by our MC-ASM on pathology cases in the FastMRI+ dataset.

highlighted areas in the uncertainty maps with the annotated lesions and abnormalities, even though the majority of the regions with high uncertainty correspond to areas of higher intensity and align with aliased reconstruction in the horizontal direction. In Fig. 11 Case 1, the uncertainty map clearly highlights the area of the bone lesion, which is large and well-separated from the aliased content. In contrast, Case 2, which involves smaller pathology areas aligned within aliased regions, shows less obvious markings on the uncertainty map. These observations have demonstrated the potential utility of uncertainty maps in clinical diagnostic settings.

Comprehensive ablation experiments have been performed to evaluate the validity of model components. The use of wavelets (both WDown/WUp and WAMSS) has shown significant benefits to reconstruction with minimal increases in network size for our proposed MambaMIR. However, the utilisation of the wavelet has shown varied tendencies among different methods. For DiffuseRecon, the utilisation of wavelet components has improved the reconstruction effectiveness, while the integration of wavelet components has adversely affected the reconstruction quality for SwinMR and STGAN. The primary cause of this divergence may be attributed to differences in network architecture. SwinMR and STGAN are based on a “plain” structure.

⁵ <https://github.com/microsoft/fastmri-plus>.

Using WRSTB across all stages is equivalent to a reduction in the 75% sequence length, since only the “LL” component is passed to the transformer block, therefore, leading to a performance drop. However, the U-Net in DiffuseRecon is based on a hierarchical structure, which is similar to our MambaMIR. The wavelet decomposition improves the power of U-Net, subsequently enhancing the reconstruction of DiffuseRecon.

Original VMamba (Liu et al., 2024) discarded the paradigm of *Norm* → *Attention* → *Norm* → *MLP* from Vision Transformer (Dosovitskiy et al., 2020); instead, they only used *Norm* → *Vision State Space Block* for lighter network architecture. According to Fig. 7, ablation studies have shown that it is still necessary to retain the MLP in our MambaMIR for medical image reconstruction, although it greatly increases network size. In addition, the utilisation of the self-attention module in the bottleneck effectively has improved the performance without significantly increasing the model size.

The choice of hyperparameter across the patch size, the training resolution, as well as the number of deep embedding channels, has also been evaluated and presented in Fig. 7(A). Patch size is an essential parameter for low-level tasks such as medical image reconstruction. Smaller patches can capture finer details since they focus on smaller regions, ensuring better reconstruction fidelity. However, the computational cost increases significantly when the number of patches to process multiplies (Huang et al., 2022a). Our ablation studies have shown a similar trend in the relationship between the choice of patch size, the resulting reconstruction performance, and the computational cost. Moreover, it can be observed that the computational complexity of MambaMIR approximately increases linearly with the length of the sequence, which is consistent with theoretical predictions of Mamba’s complexity.

In terms of the number of latent space channels (#Channel) in S6, typically, for low-level tasks, the performance increases and finally becomes stable (or drops) as #Channel increases. A larger latent space can provide a model with a higher capacity to encode complicated features and details of the input images, which generally allows for more detailed and accurate reconstructions, especially for complex images with a lot of variance. However, models with a very high-dimensional latent space can risk overfitting, particularly if the training data is limited or not diverse enough, which leads to a performance drop. Ablation studies have shown that both the model performance and the corresponding computation cost increase as #Channel increases, however, no performance drop has been observed when #Channel is large. This reflects that our proposed MambaMIR has the potential to achieve better performance with higher-dimensional latent space.

Random cropping during model training is a common data augmentation technique that can significantly affect the final results of the model. Typically, random cropping helps to prevent overfitting by ensuring that the model does not learn to rely on specific features located in particular parts of an image. While random cropping increases robustness and generalisation, it might also lead to a loss of important contextual information when the cropping region is too small. Ablation studies have shown that the reconstruction performance initially improves, reaching an optimal value before subsequently declining as the training resolution increases, where the optimal performance is a balance of data augmentation and information richness for a single crop.

To further explore the potential of the Mamba-based model as a competitor to the Transformer, a fair comparison between our MambaMIR and its Transformer counterparts has been conducted. As illustrated in Fig. 7(B), it can be observed that applying self-attention (without the window mechanism) in the shallow and high-resolution stage is extremely computationally expensive due to its quadratic complexity. From ‘S3T1’ to ‘SOT4’, more self-attention modules are applied, which leads to an extensive increase of computational complexity meanwhile pushing the balance from better fidelity to better perception following a Perception-Distortion Trade-off (Blau and Michaeli, 2018). The proposed MambaMIR has shown superiority over all different Transformer-based counterparts in terms of two trade-offs: Perception-Distortion Trade-off and Performance-Complexity Trade-off.

6. Conclusion

In conclusion, our proposed MambaMIR and MambaMIR-GAN represent significant advances in the field of medical image reconstruction. The proposed generalised framework has achieved superior performance on fast MRI, SVCT, and LDPET, which proves its scalability and potential for other reconstruction applications such as ultrasound or low-dose CT reconstruction. Our proposed MC-ASM mechanism demonstrates its superiority over the commonly used MC dropout, providing reliable uncertainty estimation without the need for hyperparameter tuning, while mitigating the performance drop often seen when using dropout for low-level tasks.

Future studies may investigate the scalability of these models for various imaging modalities and their potential for computational efficiency.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jiahao Huang: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Liutao Yang:** Visualization, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Fanwen Wang:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Investigation, Data curation. **Yinzhe Wu:** Validation, Investigation, Data curation. **Yang Nan:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Project administration, Formal analysis. **Weiwen Wu:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Chengyan Wang:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Kuangyu Shi:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Angelica I. Aviles-Rivero:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology. **Carola-Bibiane Schönlieb:** Supervision, Resources, Methodology. **Daoqiang Zhang:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Guang Yang:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Acknowledgements

This study was supported in part by the ERC IMI (101005122), the H2020 (952172), the Medical Research Council (MC/PC/21013), National Natural Science Foundation of China (62201628 and 62471502), the Royal Society (IEC\NSFC\211235), the NVIDIA Academic Hardware Grant Program, the SABER project supported by Boehringer Ingelheim Ltd, NIHR Imperial Biomedical Research Centre (RDA01), Wellcome Leap Dynamic Resilience, UKRI guarantee funding for Horizon Europe MSCA Postdoctoral Fellowships (EP/Z002206/1), and the UKRI Future Leaders Fellowship (MR/V023799/1).

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